

THE PROCESS OF ENGLISH TEACHING AND LEARNING AT COURSE INSTITUTION

Leny Saili Rahmah
Universitas Islam Nusantara

Abstract

Teaching is interactive process, in which the teacher's method is the result from interaction process among the teacher, the learners, the instructional task, and activities overtime. Course is one of alternative for students who want to study English deeply, more detail, specifically to improve English skills as an addition English lesson at the school. This research aims to describe the process of English teaching and learning at one of course institution as non-formal education at Beginner level of POLITEK IBC Indramayu. Beside that, it is done to identify students' supporting factor to study English at course institution. The descriptive method is used in the study by applying the qualitative analysis with the specification on the description. This paper uses some techniques for getting information or facts by observation and interviewing. Some questionnaires for teacher, learners, officers and director are given as well. The finding showed that the students support factors to study English at POLITEK IBC are because the methods which are used by POLITEK IBC are suitable with capabilities people of Indramayu. The teacher of beginner level can be called as effective teacher, they use six principles which is used by the effective teacher, namely: (1) daily review (2) new material (3) guided practice (4) specific feedback (5) independent practice (6) weekly and monthly review. Students' motivation to study English at POLITEK IBC because they consider that POLITEK IBC has good quality. It shows from achievement of POLITEK IBC, for several times it has won institution competition. There are seven activities in teaching learning of POLITEK IBC; Sunday meeting, general meeting and grand meeting, speaking class, writing class, reading class and listening class.

Keywords: English teaching learning, Course Institution

Introduction

As an international language, English is necessary for all people in the world from children until adult. Although English lesson has applied from the elementary school up to university as formal education but students do not feel enough to get English lesson yet. That is why many students want to learn English course in non-formal education. Non-formal education includes course institution, training institution, play group, and so on. Non-formal education is organized for society who needs education service. The function of non-formal education is as substitute, addition, and or complement of formal education in the framework of education support along live.

POLITEK IBC is non-formal education and one of English courses in Indramayu regency. Beside English course, computer class, Mobile Phone Technician, and Japanese Course are available at POLITEK IBC. The institution has been existed since 1984 until now, although the existence of POLITEK IBC in the small town in Indramayu regency but in 2006 POLITEK IBC followed English competition of a model skill and education institution in West Java level and becomes the runner up. Besides that, it has ever been a winner in competition of institution's management. It is interesting to investigate and to analyze the process of English teaching learning at POLITEK IBC.

Based on the background above, this investigation can be formulated by the questions as follows: How does the process of English teaching and learning in beginner level in POLITEK IBC? What are the students' supporting factors to study English at POLITEK IBC?

One of components that support English teaching and learning process is the method. As stated previously, this component has a very important role and meaning in English teaching

learning process. The success of learning teaching cannot be reached without involving it. In term, the output will be qualified if the whole components are integrated, on the contrary, the education system will result in failure when the whole components are not accordance.

As we know that methodology is very significant component of language teaching. It is supporting the successful of language teaching. Approach, method, and technique are the other components that support English teaching learning process. Learning English at a course is different from learning English at a school.

It will be different the methods of English teaching learning as formal education and non-formal education. The characteristic of formal education is obligatory for Indonesia society and nowadays the compulsory education for Indonesia society to study (formal education) for nine years. Whereas, the characteristics of non-formal education mot only as addition and complement of non- formal education, but also the characteristic of non-formal education as substitution of formal education.

English course at POLITEK IBC is as complement and addition for students who study at Elementary School (SD), Junior High School (SMP), and Senior High School (SMA), whereas English course is as substitution for graduate students who can not continue their study and the learning level at course will be different depending on skill of students themselves.

Literature Review

TEFL or Teaching English as a Foreign Language refers to teach English to students whose first language is not English and is taught in a region where English is not the dominant language. TEFL usually occurs in the student's own country either within the state school system, or private, either in an after-hours language school or with a one-on-one tutor. The teachers may be native or non-native speakers of English.

Language is part of education. Since English becomes a major international language, the demand for mastering English has increased. This put a considerable force to educational resources of many countries, including Indonesia. Problem relating to the teaching of English are discussed, identified, and formulated. These cover curriculum, methodology, and the role of cognitive and affective factor in the acquisition process. Language teaching also involves a number of components, such as policy, approach, syllabus, material, classroom, teacher and learners. These components connect to each other to form a good language teaching.

Based on ELT English become the language that is used in teaching and learning process. Language teaching as the activity, which is intended to bring about learning. It at least involves three disciplines: linguistics, psychology, and pedagogy. Linguistics provides information about language in general and the specific language being taught; psychology describes how learning takes place; pedagogy blends the information from linguistics and psychology into a compatible method of presentation in the classroom in order to easy learn for students. Based on this, teaching method is regarded as the important aspect of pedagogy.

In the education area, teaching, learning, instruction, and curriculum are connected each other. Teaching is reflection of teacher identity system measure as professional; learning is reflections of students' identity system are showed by action which is connected with assignment which is given; instruction is social system the place for teaching and learning activities; whereas curriculum is social system pointed to lesson plan.

Effective teachers have clear and consistent communication and management skills. They use classroom time effectively and efficiently either on instruction or on student task development. As a definition of teacher, teacher is called on to be a guide or facilitator. Based on Myra Pollack Sadker and David Miller Sadker (2005) there are six principles which is used by effective teacher because the principles are consistently and systematically. They are: (1) daily review (2) new material (3) guided practice (4) specific feedback (5) independent practice (6) weekly and monthly review

1. Daily Review.

At the beginning of the lesson, teachers review prior learning. Frequently, teachers focus on assigned homework, clarify points of confusion, and provide extra practice for facts and skills that need more attention.

2. New Material.

Teacher begins by letting students know the objective to be attained; new information is broken down into smaller bits and covered at a brisk pace. Teacher illustrates main points with concrete examples. Teachers ask questions frequently to check for student understanding and to make sure that students are ready for independent work using new skills and knowledge.

3. Guided Practice.

Students use new skills and knowledge under direct teacher supervision. During guided practice, teachers ask many content questions and many process questions. Teachers check students' responses for understanding, offering prompts and providing corrective feedback. Guided practice continues until students answer with approximately 70 to 80 percent accuracy.

4. Specific feedback.

Correct answers to questions are acknowledged clearly, so that students will understand when their work is accurate. When student answers are hesitant, the teacher provides process feedback ("Yes, Juanita, that's correct because..."). Teacher correct inaccurate responses immediately, before errors become habitual. Frequent errors are a sign that students are not ready for independent work, and guided practice should continue.

5. Independent Practice.

Independent practice similar to guided practice, except that students work by themselves at their seats or at home. Independent practice continues until responses are assured, quick, and at a level of approximately 95 percent accuracy.

6. Weekly and monthly reviews.

Regular reviews offer students the opportunity for more practice, a strategy related to high achievement.

Based on Robert O'Neill circa 1980 goals can be classified by type and status. Type involve: cognitive, affective and psycho motor. Status involves: short term (Teach a few examples of the most frequent questions we use to get information from and about other people's job, nationality, where/live); mid term (Extend outwards to other functions such as inquiring into cause, asking about like/dislike. At the same time begin to contrast systematically the difference in construction between simple and progressive Qs); and, Long term (Help the learner towards generative competence in giving and getting information about oneself and other people, asking for things, suggestion things, offering and refusing things. Relate these utterances to the structural principles underlying them: Tense, Word order, Modality)

Many basic mistakes are made by teachers because they do not pay enough attention to affective goals and they fail to distinguish sufficiently in their own teaching and analysis of other people's teaching and materials between long/mid/short term goals.

Strategies in teaching beginner are divided as three strategies. They are: Expository, Eliciting, and Integrative.

Expository strategy involves: explaining; focusing; Problem-setting; exemplification; correcting and Model-Giving; summarizing

Eliciting strategy involves: questions; Drilling; Role-Simulation; Repetition; Recall; Modeling; Silence

Integrative strategy involves: Linking lesson-segments to lessons; linking lesson-segments to block of lessons; linking blocks of lesson to overall goals; establishing rapport with the class; and, establishing rapport and interaction between members of the class

The scope of English subject involves reading, listening, writing, speaking, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and spelling. Those materials have been lined in the curriculum of POLITEK IBC as non-formal education. A bit detail of them as follows:

o Reading

Reading methods are most effective when reading materials are based on real-life, natural setting. Reading should be approached first of all as a process for deriving meaning from the printed word and not for using the printed word as a stimulus for speaking. Reading aloud tends to encourage students to respond to the surface features of the language and not to the message.

- Writing

Writing language has become one more tool of communication. Practically, writing activities involves copying sentences have mastered, arranging words to be sentences, writing sentences by changing a certain element of it. Arranging the words to be correct sentences, concluding: a history, private experiences, and writing a simple composition

- Listening

Listening comprehension is one of the hardest skills to learn in a foreign language. Within the framework of communication, listening skills take on a very important role. They are both of basis for the development of all other skills and the main channel through which the student makes initial contact with the target language and its culture.

- Speaking

Beauchamp (1968: 322) in Imani (2005) said that “speaking is the second communication skill that the children learn”.

- Grammar

In this part of teaching English, teacher teaches the students to understand grammatically rules, in other that the students can use English from communication correctly in spoken language or in written.

- Vocabulary

Vocabulary is the one of important materials that should be learned, because it is the basic aspect in language. And their ability in English is determined little or much vocabulary.

- Pronunciation

Pronunciation is part of speaking. There are many students find a lot of difficulties in conversation because they don't know how to pronounce English fluently.

- Spelling

Spelling is one of important factor in learning English, especially for the new students. Spelling is part of speaking.

Method

The descriptive method used in the study is by applying the qualitative analysis with the specification on the description. Guba and Lincoln quoted by Moleong (2000:15) state that “qualitative research called with the naturalistic inquiry”. In qualitative research, the study uses descriptive qualitative method. According to Milan (1998:395) “qualitative method is inquiry which the researcher collects the data in face to face situation, by interacting with selected person in their setting (field research)”.

Descriptive method is similar to the structural method; its research method is used for solving the currently problem and it involves investigating, classifying, analyzing, and deciding the problem.

This paper uses some techniques for getting information or facts by observation and interviewing some students who study at beginner level of POLITEK IBC, teachers and director of POLITEK IBC. Some questionnaires are given for some learners to know their escalation in English lesson as long as study at POLITEK IBC, and deciding location or sample.

Observation is a systematic and accurate research and it describes the objective data that has been and got research in location directly. This technique is used for getting information concerning to the objective condition of POLITEK IBC. The investigation will seek the empirical data that will be observed in order to find out the general situation and condition at POLITEK IBC.

Interview technique is an oral communication technique; it is used for collecting the data through the way to do the communication directly. Interview is to display the language proficiency of one participant, and interview is a technique of verbal communication for getting information. The technique that is used for collecting data is through the way to do communication directly. This interview is dedicated to: 1) director or owner, to know the history of POLITEK IBC, method which is used, and general description concerning the general process

of teaching and learning English course for beginner level at POLITEK IBC; 2) instructors, to know all the activities of English teaching and learning process, method which is used in teaching and learning process; and, 3) students, to know the interest, difficulties and the outcome of teaching English.

The research took place at POLITEK IBC Jl. Tentara Pelajar no 3 Jatibarang Kab. Indramayu. The choice to select this place because to know the process of teaching learning at English course institution, wants to know why this Institution has been existing since 1984 until now although the existence in the small town in Indramayu regency and why this institution have some achievements. May be from this research being able to learn in the future how to implement the good methods for course, and also can learn how the ways to exist of institution for a long time.

Result and Discussion

The general descriptions of the course are below:

Name	: POLITEK IBC
Address	: Jl. Tentara Pelajar No. 3 Jatibarang-Indramayu West Java Indonesia
English Classroom	: 3 classroom
Learning Time	: Monday – Saturday
	1. 8 a.m – 10 a.m
	2. 10 a.m - 12 p.m
	3. 1 p.m - 3 p.m
	4. 3 p.m - 5 p.m

Students who study English at POLITEK IBC are expected to practice their English ability, from beginner level until Elementary Two leve.

Almost students consider that classroom of POLITEK IBC is suitable place to practice English than in the house or school.

Almost every week there are new students at POLITEK IBC especially on July-December, together with new school year. Every student who has registered will be collected first up to 10-15 students, and then they can begin study English. Usually, to collect students up to 10-15 needs a week along. Before studying English they must follow placement test first to know their ability.

Based on students of beginner's opinion (it is gotten from questioners paper), Almost students said that the teacher of POLITEK IBC especially Beginner's teacher is the good teacher. The quality of teacher is very good; the way to transfer material is easy to be understood. The teacher is familiar as well. There are many increasing that is gotten by students about English lesson in school during they have been studying English at POLITEK IBC. It resembles with Myra Pollack Sadker and David Miller Sadker's opinion (2005); there are six principles which are used by effective teacher because the principles are consistently and systematically. They are: (1) Daily review; (2) New material; (3) Guided practice; (4) Specific feedback; (5) Independent practice; and, (6) Weekly and monthly review.

Based on observation that is done, the researcher found :

1. Teacher does daily review every day, before finishing English learning such as give some question for students, about material which is given just now. It similar with daily review
2. Each meeting teacher always gives new material (it is found by researcher for three meeting) it similar with new material
3. Teacher guides students well every meeting. More over for silent student, teacher tries to make he or she be confident person. It similar with guide practice
4. Before beginning study, usually teacher gives question for students about last meeting material. It similar with specific feedback

5. Teacher gives 30 minutes every practice class to conversation with friend and sometimes gives assignment to practice English with other person at home. It similar with independent practice

6. Every month teacher gives monthly test, it similar to weekly and monthly review

From this observation, the study concludes that beginner level teacher of POLITEK IBC is effective teacher because the six principles above has been doing, especially during the observation is done.

In teaching learning English process, teacher is using media such as books, texts, cassettes, videos, games, pictures, and school environment. The most prestigious media that used at POLITEK IBC is language-based environment. It is referred to Gerland and Ely's opinion (in Arsyad, 1997:3) they say, "The teachers, textbooks, and school environment are including media in teaching and learning process".

Media for language environment is also called as natural language laboratory. The students will heard and speak the language patterns in the conversation directly and effectively. They will put some English words or English sentences in daily language.

As non-formal education, POLITEK IBC is the place for people who want to increase their skill especially in English skill. It seen from the number of students in the class, usually in the formal education there are more than 30 students, but at course such as POLITEK IBC as non-formal education there are 15 (maximum) students and the minimum students are 5 students. It does in order to teaching and learning process is more intensive. Also the process of teaching and learning is different, it seen from; usually at the school as formal education, the most activities of students when study English are answer the work book. Teacher, just around 15 minutes explains the lesson after that students answer the workbook (LKS) or answer question from teacher. (Observation at SDN Palalangan-Bandung, SMPN 1 Cilengkrang, and researcher's experience when Elementary school, Junior High School, and Senior High School). Whereas, the process of teaching and learning English in the course, such as POLITEK IBC as non-formal education is direct method.

The relationship among the teacher and students is like friend; it is not like among teacher and students. Also among students and students, whereas every students are different age (usually beginner level consists of elementary students and Junior High School students, but sometimes there are from Senior High School, depends on their ability) like friend who have same age.

Students activities

Students learn English at POLITEK IBC twice in a week. They study in the class. Beside that there are three activities which are done once a month. They are Sunday meeting, general meeting and grand meeting. Students of POLITEK IBC study about English basic, they are speaking, listening, reading, and writing. The name of subject are speaking class, writing class, reading class and listening class.

speaking class

Practice is the key to improve speaking skill. Daily conversation practice plays a vital role in speaking; practice is the main way to acquire English. This activity is giving the opportunity for the students to practice English; because language is habitual process, so, without practice it is impossible to learn speaking or to learn language. Every meeting conversation helps students in pronunciation. Practice also makes students confident and fluent in speaking.

At POLITEK IBC the teacher uses English as guide language, teacher is as guide. Teacher use action to make student more understand what he or she says or use mix language, between English and mother tongue. In this subject the most available technique of teaching English is focused on conversation and practice technique. In this activity, Teacher gives dialogue then translate together with students and then students practice that dialog with their friends and also their teacher (usually the dialog about daily activities, using the name of something in the class in other to students can practice it). All students must speak up. First session, students read their book about the dialogue then in second session student do not read that dialogue, teacher guide

them, especially for students who do not remember yet. In the dialogue class, students learn speaking, listening, spelling, and pronunciation in one meeting.

a. writing class

The second activity is writing class. Writing relate with grammar. Students learn grammar in other to when they write sentence or essay English, they know how to write well. In beginner level, the grammar is not complex yet. Just as introduction. Students are though how to make simple sentence. Such as make sentence use simple present tense, continuous tense, how to use demonstrative pronoun. And so on.

Beside learn grammar, in writing class, students learn how to write vocabularies. Teacher says a word, then student write down. After that, they make sentence use that word. Example: "apple", students write this is apple, I eat apple, apple is red, and so on.

b. Reading class

In the reading class, teacher gives a text. Students read loud one by one. After that teacher ask do students understand about the meaning of the text or not, then translate together, to know what the text means. There are some questions about the text which must be answered by students. When students answer the questions, teacher takes a walk to students' chair, to guide them.

c. Listening class

In the Listening class, there are two kinds of learn listening. The first is traditional way, and the audio visual way. In the traditional way, students listen the teacher's say. In the audio visual way, students listen and watch VCD or DVD about English conversation. But for beginner level, students listen and watch conversation on VCD, the speaker is Indonesian people. Because students' ability still low, so if they listen native speaker, they will difficult to understand it.

d. Sunday meeting

As its name, Sunday meeting does at Sunday in every two weeks. Usually, it is conducted at 9 a.m. this activity is conducted for three times. Who follows this activity are members of POLITEK IBC. Example, for first week is all students of beginner level from all sorts of class, and then next meeting is Elementary One level, then next meeting Elementary Two level.

The material of Sunday meeting are introduction, speech, puzzle game. All activities are full English, and beginner level try to practice speak English.

e. General meeting

General meeting is an activity that is followed by all of level from Beginner until Elementary Two. It is done every two month. The activities similar with Sunday meeting

f. Grand meeting

Grand meeting is an activity that is followed by all of level from beginner, Elementary One until Elementary Two. It is similar with general meeting. It is done every six month.

All of activities are the out class activities such as Sunday meeting, general meeting and grand meeting is done in other to between students of POLITEK IBC to know each other.

Conclusion

After analyzing and observing the process of learning and teaching at POLITEK IBC. The researcher can conclude that English teaching and learning at POLITEK IBC especially in beginner level uses Grammar Translation Method and Direct Method. Although Grammar Translation Method is the old method (because it begun to be taught in educational institutions in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries) but at POLITEK IBC, it is still as a good method. Because the suitable method is depends on learners' capability. Whatever method which is used must be adapted with capability and environment of learners. When teacher teach beginner, should use mix language between mother tongue and English in order to learners understands what teacher said, or use body language as substitute mother tongue to more learners accustomed. Direct method is used when students learn speaking class, this method helps students easy to absorb speaking subject. The methods which are used depends on material will be transferred by teacher.

The students support factors to study English at POLITEK IBC are because the methods which are used by POLITEK IBC are suitable with capabilities people of Indramayu. Beside The teacher of beginner level can be called as effective teacher, they use six principles which is used by the effective teacher, namely: (1) daily review (2) new material (3) guided practice (4) specific feedback (5) independent practice (6) weekly and monthly review. And also students motivate to study English at POLITEK IBC because they consider that POLITEK IBC has good quality. It shows from achievement of POLITEK IBC, for several times it has won institution competition.

References

- Alwasilah, A.C. (1993). *Pengantar Sosiologi Bahasa*. Bandung: Angkasa
- Beauchamp, G.A. (1965). *Basic Dimensions of Elementary Method*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Brown, H.D. (1994). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall regent.
- Curtain, H.A. & Pesola, C.A. (1988). *Languages and Children Making the Match: Foreign Language Instruction in the Elementary School*. United State: Addison-Wesley.
- Echols, J.M. & Shadily, H. (1989). *Kamus Indonesia Inggris* (3rd ed.). Jakarta: Gramedia
- Larsen-Freeman, D. (1986). *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. England: Oxford University Press
- Hutchinson, T. & Waters, A. (1987). *English for Specific Purpose: A Learning Centered Approach*. Cambridge University Press
- Imani, A. (2005). *The Implementation of Teaching English Speaking at Conversation Club (A Dscriptive Study at The Center Jl. Setiabudi No.26B Bandung)*. Unpublished Paper.
- Jahidin, R.H. (1985). *Beginner*. Indramayu: IBC group
- Johnson, E.B. (2002). *Contextual Teaching and Learning: Menjadikan Kegiatan Belajar-Mengajar Mengasyikan dan Bermakna*. Bandung: Mizan Learning Center
- Moleong, L.J. (2000). *Methodology Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Reed, A.J.S, et al. (1998). *In The Classroom: An Introduction To Education*. Boston: Mc Graw Hill
- Richards, J.C. & Rodgers, T.S. (1986). *Approaches and Methods in language Teaching; A description and Analysis*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- O'Neill, R.(1978). Kernel One [Online] available at: www.btinternet.com/~ted.power/teflindex.htm (April, 129 2008)
- Sadker, M.P. & Sadker, D.M. (2005). *Teachers, School, and Society*
- Tompkins, G.E & Hoskisson, K. (1991). *Language Art: Content and Teaching Strategies*. New York: Maxwell Macmilian